

Technology and AI for Workplace Inclusion in EY (Ernst and Young)

Raga Keerthika M

Assistant Professor, Jain College, Vasavi Road Bangalore – 560004

Abstract

Exploring the crucial role of technology and artificial intelligence in order to analyse and help in making the workplace more inclusive. By analysing the use of artificial intelligence in order to review job descriptions through inclusive language, and how virtual reality training programs can be used to build empathy and cultural awareness through training. It also shows how data analytics could track and improve the diversity across an organization. EY (Ernst and Young) is utilizing these tools in order to make their hiring process fairer and to create a more inclusive culture. By analysing employee engagement and using AI-driven solutions, they aim to support better decision making and spark innovation. The main objective of the research is to provide everyone equal opportunities and to bring in diverse ideas that can boost performance on the global competitiveness. The research will utilize a combination of quantitative and qualitative data collection methods. To understand the impact, this research will include surveys, interviews and document analysis.

Keywords: Employee engagement, work environment, technological advancements, workplace inclusivity.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence plays a major role in reshaping the workplace and emerging new trends across the companies by adopting the usage of AI tools. It plays a vital role in upbringing core competencies, improving the production of the company. AI automates repetitive tasks and provides smart assistance, it helps in hiring and talent management process. Technology plays a significant role in the organizations. Technology provides a hybrid and remote working conditions for both employees and employers. It enhances cyber security in order to identify unusual activities in real-time.

Workplace inclusion is the fundamental principle in developing responsible and effective technology. It would create a friendly environment at the work, so that all the employees would feel much more valued, respected, supported and fully able to participate and interact with one another in the work arena. With the rise of technology Wipro company has

been recognized for implementing various programs like mentorship, equitable career growth, promoting diversity and taking in various actions in order to reduce gender pay gap.

MathCo is another company emphasizing in building equitable career pathways for its employees and it strives in providing a better work environment. Mathco understands that only a balanced team fuels innovation. Infosys BPM utilizes artificial intelligence in order to revolutionize Human Resource operations; it mainly aims to remove biases from hiring processes. The company utilizes AI-powered tools to support personalized learning and monitors employee well-being in order to promote a culturally intelligent work-force. Microsoft utilizes AI-powered tools for the visually impaired and for dyslexia employees. Equiv is another Startup company that utilizes artificial intelligence in order to promote unbiased hiring practices. It has helped over 800 diversity hires which includes

women, persons with disabilities veterans and LGBT S and LGBTQ + individuals.

This organization facilitates Career firs which was tailored to different communities to promote inclusivity.

HISTORY

Ernst and Young (EY) company is a multinational firm located in Bangalore. This company began its journey in 1989 by globally merging “Ernst and Arthur Young and Co”. It provides professional services for tax assurance and transactions. It is one of the “Big Four” accounting firms in Bangalore. In different countries it operates as a network of firms. In Bengaluru, EY has thrived on the growth of the Indian economy. Over the past 150 years, EY Company is the result of multiple mergers of predecessor companies. It was mainly established by Harding and Pullien in England in the year 1849. An accountant called Frederick Whinney became a partner ten years later.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To analyse the effectiveness of AI tools in recruitment and performance management.
- To explore how technology and artificial intelligence (AI) can enhance workplace inclusions at EY.
- To analyse how data analytics could measure the impact of inclusion initiatives and guide them in continuous improvement.
- To understand employee perceptions regarding the inclusion focused technologies at EY.
- To provide recommendations for optimising and to create a more inclusive workplace culture.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Yanting, Zou and Muhammad Ali. “Artificial Intelligence, Digital Finance and

Financial Inclusion: A Conceptual Framework.” In Financial Inclusion Across Asia: Bringing Opportunities for Business, edited by C.-M Leong, Muhammad Ali, S. A. Raza, C.-H. Puah, and I. H. Eksi, 77-85. Leeds: Emerald Publishing Limited, 2023.

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374197643>

AI is analysing the financial industry by becoming more accessible and inclusive. It makes credit scoring better using alternative data, enabling people with fewer credit records.

This increases the financial access for poor people and the unbanked. Identity verification by AI makes transactions safer. These systems tend to prevent fraud and establish user trust. Not everyone is equally favoured due to the digital divide and still accessing technology and digital literacy seems to be an obstacle. The exclusion narrows the coverage of AI-based financial solutions. Greater loan accessibility through AI is a cause for over borrowing concerns.

Individuals may accumulate unaffordable debt without fully realizing it. There may be concerns about data security and privacy which are growing in the field of digital banking. With the growth of digital services, user data must be protected. Research on the role of AI inclusion highlights the benefits and difficulties that AI presents to the financial industry. In the ongoing effort to balance innovation and to provide equitable access, the research contributes.

Jameel, Kiran and Laeeq Janjua. “Harnessing Artificial Intelligence for Digital Financial Inclusion.” The Critical Review of Social Science Studies (2024). <https://doi.org/10.59075/c00w3s24> Artificial Intelligence significantly improves digital financial inclusion (DFI), which engages marginalized and it helps in

boosting participation among women, youth, underbanked communities and in small businesses. It indicates low-income groups in financial systems. It enables financial institutions to serve better in excluded populations. It helps in analysing and organizing disordered data, helps in decision-making in financial services. Artificial intelligence helps in fostering user trust in the digital platforms; it strengthens cybersecurity and helps in detecting frauds. It analyses and organizes disordered data, helping in decision-making in financial sectors. AI-powered chatbots provide user-friendly financial assistance and support. Thus, assumed technological access and literacy may not be realistic in all regions. The authors concluded a large-scale AI adoption is required in order to drive financial inclusion globally. Long term effects of artificial intelligence financial inclusion remain underexplored. Future research should mainly focus on customised artificial intelligence solutions for diverse populations. For building inclusive financial ecosystems cross-sector collaboration is very crucial. AI offers a Transformative potential but it requires thoughtful implementation.

Omogbeme, Angela, and Oyindamola Modupe Odewuyi. "Mitigating AI Bias in Financial Decision-Making: A DEI Perspective." *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews* 24, no. 3 (2024): 1822-1838. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.2.4.3.3894>

In this paper, a strategic framework was introduced in order to align the AI applications with diversity, inclusion goals. A transparent system would be essential to allow scrutiny of decisions and to reveal the hidden biases. The research paper mainly emphasizes that a limited scope could affect broader findings across different contexts. It provides a guidance for creating bias-aware, trustworthy AI

systems. It also proposes steps for ethical development of artificial intelligence in financial decision-making processes. Thus, the road map focuses on fairness, inclusivity, and transparency in the AI models. By bridging innovation with ethics, it is an essential way to make AI a tool for equity. Without ethical oversight, artificial intelligence may unintentionally worsen and in financial sectors. Thus, the study provides appropriate insights for using AI responsibly in the financial sectors.

Espana-Rivadeneira, Martina, Luis Fernando Taruchain-Pozo, Aracelly Fernanda Nunez-Naranjo and Diego Escobar-Bermudes.

"Work environment and its influences on organisational commitment: A study in the financial sector" *Journal of Educational and Social Research* 15, no. 1 (January 5, 2025): 198. <https://doi.org/10.36941/jesr-2025-0015>. <https://www.richtmann.org/journal/index.php/jesr/article/view/14138>

In this paper the author studies by surveying 200 administrative staffs from a single financial institution, by using purposive sampling. The study limits the generalisation of results and introduces potential bias due to the non-random selection of participants. This research mainly focuses on three dimensions of work climate: autonomy, equity and transparency. The findings of the paper reveal significant positive associations between the chosen dimensions and employee engagement. The paper suggests a few improvements in order to enhance organizational loyalty. It aims to cultivate a more inclusive and supportive workplace culture. It emphasizes the importance of considering demographic factors and it mainly encourages further exploration and it provides tailored interventions in order to strengthen employee engagement in the financial

sectors.

METHODOLOGY

A Google form based structured online survey was created and disseminated. The study's sample was drawn from employees of Ernest and Young (EY) Company were chosen at random using the random sampling technique. The responder received the questionnaire by email, and the sample size consists of 150 individuals. The response rate, with 124 responses, was 82.66%.

DATA INTERPRETATION

The Technology and Artificial Intelligence for Workplace Inclusion in EY (Ernst and Young)

a. What was EY's primary approach to promoting financial inclusion in India?

EY's primary approach to promote financial inclusion in India is interested

- ❖ 72.7% believe it's collaborating with fintech companies to enhance digital financial services.
- ❖ 18.2% think it's establishing rural banks
- ❖ 9.1% think it's limiting services to urban areas
- ❖ 0% selected believe providing direct subsidies to low-income households.

b. According to EY, which digital payment method is most preferred in rural and semi urban India?

- ❖ 80% of them selected a unified payment interface.
- ❖ 20% selected cash transactions
- ❖ No respondent chose credit cards or cheque payments

Thus, UPI is seen as the most preferred method, with smaller groups

choosing cash transactions and a very few or none choosing credit cards or cheque payments.

c. How effective do you believe virtual collaboration tools are in promoting inclusion among geographically dispersed teams in EY?

- ❖ 54.5% found them very effective.
- ❖ 27.3% found them moderately effective.
- ❖ 9.1% found them slightly effective.
- ❖ 9.1% found them not at all effective. This indicates that most of them had believed in virtual collaboration tools promoting inclusion among geographical dispersed teams in EY.

d. How effective do you believe virtual collaboration tools are in promoting inclusion among geographically dispersed teams at EY?

- ❖ 54.5% of respondents believe virtual collaboration tools are very effective in promoting inclusion among geographically dispersed teams in EY.
- ❖ 27.3% find these tools moderately effective.
- ❖ 9.1% think they are slightly effective.
- ❖ And 9.1% say they are not at all effective.

e. What is EY's initiative to recruit neurodivergent individuals in India called?

- ❖ 81.8% respondents opted for Neurodiversity hiring programme.
- ❖ 9.1% each goes to the Inclusive Workforce Programme and the Equal Opportunity schemes.
- ❖ 0% represents diverse abilities initiative.

- f. How did EY modify its technical assessments for neurodivergent candidates?
- ❖ 81.8% of initiatives were focused on the Neurodiversity hiring programme.
 - ❖ 9.1% each for the Inclusive Workforce Programme and equal opportunity employment scheme.
 - ❖ 0% represent diverse abilities initiative.
- g. To what extent do you believe technology can play a role in fostering a more inclusive workplace in EY?
- ❖ 81.8% of respondents believe technology plays a vital role in fostering a more inclusive workplace at EY.
 - ❖ 18.2% believed that technology would play only a minor role.
 - ❖ 0% respondents believe technology has no role or only a moderate role in inclusion at EY.
- h. Do you believe that AI-powered tools can help in identifying and mitigating unconscious bias in workplace processes? (e.g. recruitment, performance reviews) at EY?
- ❖ 36.4% of respondents strongly disagree that AI powered tools can help identify and mitigate unconscious bias in workplace processes at EY.
 - ❖ 6.4% agree with the statement showing a positive outlook toward AI's role in bias mitigation.
 - ❖ 27.3% strongly agree that AI can help in this area.
 - ❖ 0% Respondents selected disagree indicating polarized opinions with most either strongly disagreeing or agreeing. Thus, the overall group is split between scepticism and optimism about AI's effectiveness in reducing workplace bias at EY.
- i. In what ways do you think technology could improve accessibility for employees with disabilities at EY?
- ❖ 81.8% of respondents believe technology could improve accessibility for employees with disabilities at EY by offering adaptive software and hardware.
 - ❖ 9.1% think providing better communication tools would help.
 - ❖ 9.1% selected all the above supporting a combination of solutions.
 - ❖ 0% opted for automating repetitive tasks
- Most people saw adaptive software and hardware as the key way technology could enhance accessibility at EY.
- j. Do you think AI-driven learning platforms can be tailored to meet the diverse learning needs and styles of employees at EY, thereby fostering inclusion?
- ❖ 72.7% of respondents agree that AI- driven learning platforms can be tailored to meet the diverse learning needs and styles at EY, fostering inclusion.
 - ❖ 27.3% of respondents strongly agree with the statement
 - ❖ 0% respondent selected disagree or strongly disagree, indicating overall positive sentiment towards AI driven learning for inclusion at EY.
- k. To what extent do you agree that the use of data analytics can help EY understand the impact of inclusion initiatives and identify areas for improvement?
- ❖ 72.7% of respondents agree that

data analytics can help EY understand the impact of inclusion initiatives and identify areas for improvement.

- ❖ 18.2% strongly agree with this statement.
 - ❖ 9.1% strongly disagree
 - ❖ 0% respondents for simply disagree
 - ❖ Overall, the majority supports a positive role of data analytics in this context.
- l. How concerned were you about the ethical implications and biases which might have arisen by using AI tools for workplace inclusion at EY?
- ❖ 90.9% of respondents are moderately concerned about the ethical implications and biases that might have arisen by using AI tools for workplace inclusion.
 - ❖ 9.1% are slightly concerned.
 - ❖ 0% of respondents are "not at all concerned" or "very concerned" indicating most people have a moderate level of concern, but not at the extremes.
- m. Do you believe that technology, training and support are adequately provided at EY to ensure all employees can effectively utilize inclusion focused tools?
- ❖ 72.7% of respondents agree that technology and support at EY are adequate for effectively using inclusion-focused tools.
 - ❖ 18.2% strongly agree with this statement.
 - ❖ Only 9.1% strongly disagree with this statement.
 - ❖ 0% of respondents disagree with

the above statement.

Thus, the majority had felt positive to the adequacy of training and support for inclusion tools at EY company.

- n. How likely are you in order to use technology or AI tools introduced at EY that were designed to promote workplace inclusion?
- ❖ 90.9% of the respondents opted moderately likely to actively use technology or AI tools that were introduced at EY for promoting the workplace inclusion.
 - ❖ 9.1% or not at all likely to use these tools.
 - ❖ 0% respondents choose likely or very likely, indicating most people are open to use these tools but not extremely enthusiastic.
- o. In your opinion how well does EY communicate its efforts and progress in leveraging technology for workplace inclusion under the financial inclusion framework?
- ❖ 81.8% felt that EY communicates its efforts and progress towards leveraging technology.
 - ❖ 9.1% felt that EY communicates "very well", indicating for improvement in making these efforts more accessible.
 - ❖ 9.1% believed that communication is "very poorly", showing a small but notable group had felt disconnected.
- p. Do you believe that AI-powered feedback mechanisms could provide better inclusive and unbiased performance evaluations at EY?
- ❖ 72.7% opted for AI feedback mechanisms which could provide much more inclusive and unbiased

performance evaluations at EY, it shows a strong overall support towards this technology.

- ❖ 18.2% disagree, indicates a notable minority which have reservations about the effectiveness or fairness of AI in this context
 - ❖ 9.1% strongly agree, reflecting a small but confident group who fully trust AI- driven evaluations in order to improve inclusion and reduce bias.
 - ❖ 0% strongly disagree suggesting that extreme scepticism is minimal among the participants.
- q. How comfortable are you with the idea of AI being used to analyse communication patterns within teams EY to identify potential inclusion challenges?
- ❖ 9.1% are not at all comfortable with AI being used for this purpose.
 - ❖ 72.7% are moderately comfortable, indicating a strong majority are open to AI analysis.
 - ❖ 18.2% are very comfortable showing some strong support.
 - ❖ 0% respondents felt slightly comfortable for the above context. Thus, most of the people are at least moderately comfortable with AI analysing communication patterns for inclusion challenges.
- r. How effective do you believe current data privacy and security measures EY are in safeguarding employing information when using technology for inclusion purposes?
- ❖ 90.9% believe current data privacy and security measures are very effective in safeguarding employee information when using technology

for inclusion purposes.

- ❖ 9.1% respondents felt the measures to be slightly effective.
- ❖ 0% respondents rated the measures as not at all effective or moderately effective showing overall high confidence in EY's data protection practices.

The vast majority trust EY's data privacy and security for inclusion tech.

- s. What role do you believe employees should play in providing feedback and shaping the development and implementation of technology for workplace inclusion and EY?
- ❖ 90.9% believe employees should play a significant role in providing feedback and shaping the development and implementation of workplace inclusion technology
 - ❖ 9.1% think employees should have a moderate role.
 - ❖ 0% respondents chose no role or a minor role, highlighting that everyone sees employee input as important in this process.

FINDINGS

- The neurodiversity hiring programme was the main initiative for recruiting neurodivergent divergent individuals at EY by receiving approximately 81.8% reviews from the employees.
- Majority of them felt technology played a vital role in fostering workplace inclusion.
- Data analytics was supported by most of the employees as a tool to understand the impact of inclusion initiatives and to find areas of improvement.
- EY's primary approach was to

promote financial inclusion in India by collaborating with fintech companies in order to enhance digital financial services and the use of Unified Payment Interface (UPI) as the preferred digital payment method in rural and semi urban areas.

- Ethical concerns about artificial intelligence were moderate.
- AI's capacity to identify and mitigate unconscious biases were polarised.
- EY's communication on leveraging technology for workplace inclusion was positively received, indicating effective transparency and stakeholder engagement.
- Employee engagement was positively influenced by inclusive technology practices.
- Candidate screening could enhance fairness in hiring.

LIMITATION

- This study in detail does not explain the long term impact of technology and artificial intelligence within the workplace inclusion in EY.
- Limited information about inclusion initiatives is adapted for different cultural or regional contexts within EY's global operations.

CONCLUSION

In EY company, technology and AI plays a vital role in advancing workplace inclusion, mainly in recruitment, accessibility, and employee development. The company targeted many initiatives such as neurodiversity hiring programme and the adoption of adaptive technologies, which demonstrates a proactive approach towards diversity. While there was a strong support for those efforts, concerns about AI bias and ethical implications which were persisting, mainly highlighting

the need for ongoing transparency, ethical oversight and tailored training. Overall, EY's strategic use of technology and AI combined with a supportive infrastructure position. The company aims to create a more inclusive and innovative workplace through continuous evaluation and improvement, which still remains essential for sustaining these goals.

REFERENCES

- Zou, Y., & Ali, M. (2023). *Artificial intelligence, digital finance and financial inclusion: A conceptual framework*. In C.-M. Leong, M. Ali, S. A. Raza, C.-H. Pua, & I. H. Eksi (Eds.), *Financial inclusion across Asia: Bringing opportunities for business* (pp. 77– 85). Emerald Publishing. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374197643>
- Jameel, K., & Janjua, L. R. (2024). Harnessing artificial intelligence for digital financial inclusion: Transforming economies in the era of Industry 4.0. *The Critical Review of Social Sciences Studies*, 2(2), 1436–1457. <https://doi.org/10.59075/c00w3s24> thecrsss.com
- Omogbeme, A., & Odewuyi, O. M. (2024). Mitigating AI bias in financial decision-making: A DEI perspective. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 24(3), 1822–1838. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.24.3.3894>
- España-Rivadeneira, M., Taruchain-Pozo, L. F., Núñez-Naranjo, A. F., & Escobar-Bermudes, D. (2025). Work environment and its influence on organizational commitment: A study in the financial sector. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 15(1), 198. <https://doi.org/10.36941/jesr-2025-0015> richtmann.org

- Nair, N., & Vohra, N. (2015). *Diversity and inclusion at the workplace: A review of research and perspectives* (Working Paper No. 2015-03-34). Indian Institute of Management Ahmedabad. <https://www.iima.ac.in/sites/default/files/rnpfiles/8631467072015-03-34.pdf> iima.ac.in
- Usanmaz, O. (2024, March 12). *What are the challenges of diversity in the workplace and how to mitigate them?* Qooper Blog. <https://www.qooper.io/blog/what-are-the-challenges-of-diversity-in-the-workplace-and-how-to-mitigate-them> qooper.io
- Ernst & Young. (2024). *GenAI for accessibility: More human, not less—How does Microsoft 365 Copilot impact the working experience of people living with disability and/or neurodivergence?* EY. <https://www.ey.com/content/dam/ey-unified-site/ey-com/en-uk/services/ai/documents/ey-gen-ai-for-accessibility-more-human-not-less.pdf> ey.com
- Nawrat, A. (2024, December 11). EY: 85 % of neurodivergent employees think generative AI creates a more inclusive workplace. *UNLEASH*. <https://www.unleash.ai/diversity-equity-inclusion/ey-85-of-neurodivergent-employees-think-generative-ai-creates-a-more-inclusive-workplace/> unleash.ai
- AI4ALL. (2018, September 6). *Building a diverse and inclusive AI workforce with the support of EY and the AI4ALL Advisory Board*. AI4ALL News. <https://ai4all.org/building-a-diverse-and-inclusive-ai-workforce-with-the-support-of-ey-and-the-ai4all-advisory-board/> ai4all.org
- BBC Worklife. (2024, March 20). *How EY is focusing on neurodiverse talent – and why it benefits everyone*. <https://www.bbc.com/worklife/article/20240320-ey-karyn-twaronite-neurodiversity-bbc-executive-interview>
- Ganesh, K. (2025, March 7). Inclusion examples in the workplace: Inspirations and tips to create an inclusive culture. *CultureMonkey*. <https://www.culturemonkey.io/employee-engagement/inclusion-examples/> culturemonkey.io
- Vohra, N., Chari, V., Mathur, P., Sudarshan, P., Verma, N., Mathur, N., et al. (2015). Inclusive workplaces: Lessons from theory and practice. *Vikalpa: The Journal for Decision Makers*, 40(3), 324–362. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0256090915601515>

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

- Not at all concerned
- Slightly concerned
- Moderately concerned
- Very concerned

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

- Not at all likely
- Slightly likely
- Moderately likely
- Very likely

- Very poorly
- Poorly
- Well
- Very well

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly agree

- Not at all comfortable
- Slightly comfortable
- Moderately comfortable
- Very comfortable

- Not at all effective
- Slightly effective
- Moderately effective
- Very effective

- No role
- A minor role
- A moderate role
- A significant role